

GIS-based Recommender Systems for Agriculture: a Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

In the agriculture domain, we face several challenges. Agriculture has specific requirements, given that for high yield crops several factors must be considered, such as rainfall, climate, location, season, soil characteristics, crop, and level of mechanization. Geographic Information System (GIS) is a tool that can deal with these factors and applications of Recommender Systems (RS) in agriculture, which are not fully developed and established. We present a systematic literature review aimed at describing and classifying studies on GIS-based RS for Agriculture. The approach used in this review allowed us to verify and analyze trends, as well as identify methodological approaches adopted in the last six years. The main contributions of this review are: i) a description of the most recent studies, in addition to contributions and limitations of research works; and ii) identification of gaps in the literature, as well as research challenges. This paper is intended to be useful to RS developers and researchers, in the agriculture domain.

Keywords: Agricultural Geography; Recommender Systems; GIS; Software Engineering; Precision agriculture; Spatial analysis; Systematic review; Agricultural informatics.

1 Introduction

Agriculture has specific requirements, as for high yield crops several factors must be considered, such as rainfall, climate, location, season, soil characteristics, crop, and level of mechanization, among others. Geographic Information System (GIS) is a tool that deals with these factors. According to [16], GIS technology is less used in production agriculture than in other business sectors.

Although developments were made in the last years, applications of GIS-based Recommender Systems (RS) in agriculture are not fully developed and established. As the

analyzed articles suggest, the use of GIS-based RS in the agriculture domain is still few and far between [5, 8, 4, 21].

We aim to identify, analyze, and classify works that present methods and techniques that make use of GIS or propose RS in the realm of agriculture. The main contributions of this review are:

1. Unveiling the state of the art, by describing the most recent approaches, methods, and techniques, in addition to the contributions and limitations of existing proposals; and
2. Presenting research challenges, by identifying gaps in the literature, and current and future research challenges.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: in Section 2 we describe the methodology used to carry out the review and analysis of the articles; in Section 3 we present the review classification aimed to synthesize the main contributions; in Section 4 we present a discussion on the results; in Section 5 we present the related works, i.e., literature reviews with similar objectives; and in Section 6 we present the conclusion.

2 Methodology

The methodology used in our literature review was inspired by the guidelines proposed by [12]. These guidelines were chosen because they provide a rigorous and replicable framework for conducting systematic literature reviews in software engineering and related fields. Given that GIS-based recommender systems often intersect with software engineering practices, especially in system design, evaluation, and implementation, the use of Kitchenham’s methodology helps to build a structured, transparent, and unbiased review process. This approach may enhance the reliability and comprehensiveness of the findings by clearly defining review questions, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data extraction strategies, and synthesis procedures.

We aim to answer the following research question: “*Which works present RSs using GIS in agriculture?*”

As we are interested in the bleeding edge of the research, we have focused on articles published in the last 6 years. The search for articles was conducted in two well-known computer science scientific databases (IEEE Xplore and Springer Link), using the following search string:

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(gis OR geographical OR spatial) AND (agriculture OR farming OR farm
OR agribusiness OR crop OR cultivation OR culture OR harvest OR fertilizer
OR soil) AND (recommender OR recommendation OR suggestion)
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Number of articles by year

Figure 1: Number of articles per year.

From this query, a total of 233 papers were obtained. Many of the works dealt with broader aspects of the search string terms, and after an initial analysis, 66 were selected for further investigation. Exclusion criteria, other than publication date, included:

1. Specific use in agriculture or agriculture-related;
2. Enough level of detail to extract information on the five axes of analysis used by the authors;
3. Clarity on the role of GIS in the application process.

The final selection yielded 26 articles to be fully analyzed, by considering five main factors, namely:

1. Type;
2. Goal;
3. Use on the Crop Lifecycle;
4. GIS use;
5. Presentation.

A first general analysis is presented in Figures 1 and 2, based on the final selection of articles. In Figure 1, a graph shows the number of articles per year. Most of the

world scenario.

Goal

- **Modernization (MOD)**: if the goal of the paper is to provide means of modernization to agricultural practices that do not correspond to the modern state of the business.
- **Management (MNG)**: if the paper presents a tool to improve processes that are already in a mature level of mechanization or informatization.

Use on the Crop Lifecycle

- **Soil Selection (SSL)**: if the paper deals with the characteristics of the soil, without regard to other elements of the agricultural process.
- **Crop Recommendation (CRE)**: if the proposed approach recommends a crop given the possibilities of the arable land.
- **Fertilization (FER)**: if the approach suggests fertilizers (e.g., NPK) to deal with specific deficiencies of the field.
- **Pest-control (PCT)**: if the approach recommends pesticides suitable for a given crop and the soil quality.
- **Watering (WAT)**: if the approach suggests volume and schedule of watering for production agriculture.
- **Yield Prediction (YPD)**: if the approach estimates the crop yield, by considering elements of the lifecycle's previous stages.

GIS Use

- **Climate (CLI)**: if in the approach the use of GIS was mainly aimed to deal with rainfall, temperature, climatic events, and other climate-specific subjects.
- **Soil Health (SOH)**: if in the proposal GIS was used to map soil characteristics, such as type of soil or concentration of macronutrients.
- **Comprehensive (COM)**: if the use of GIS encompassed both **CLI** and **SOH** categories.

Presentation

- **Descriptive (DES)**: if the work was described in a qualitative manner.
- **Mathematical (MAT)**: the mathematical aspects of the method are clearly stated in the article, enabling variable levels of reproduction.

4 Results

There are works dealing with on-the-field applications of GIS-based RSs [1, 3, 5, 8, 10, 11, 13, 25, 26, 28, 29, 30, 6]. These applications were in the production of rice [27], soy, maize [29, 27], potato [28], and walnut [11], among others.

In [1, 5, 8, 28, 4, 9, 17, 20, 21, 23], the applications arise from countries where the mechanization and informatization of agriculture are still evolving.

Half of the analyzed papers deal with the modernization of non-optimal agricultural practices. There is a correlation that links the papers that deal with modernization [1, 5, 8, 10, 28, 4, 9, 17, 20, 21] and focus on crop recommendation and fertilization [1, 5, 8, 10, 11, 25, 28, 29, 4, 17, 20, 21, 18, 30, 6, 27], which shows the social use of science in these works.

Most of the papers deal with two basic points: recommendation of the crop [1, 5, 8, 25, 17, 20, 27] and fertilization [10, 11, 28, 29, 4, 21, 18, 30, 6]. These are the main elements for subsistence agriculture where, for example, estimates of crop yields are of little value, and pesticides may not be readily available.

Half of the papers deal with the climate aspects stored by GIS, due to climate data being more available than the cost-demanding soil data. For example, in [14] climate data is related to the growth of crops to create an ontology-based RS, and in [15] climate data is used to predict production in response to rainfall.

Some papers deal with relevant environmental questions, such as the reclamation of land affected by mining [2] or impacted by continuous crop cultivation [23].

Most papers do not present the mathematical foundations that were used, discouraging thus the replication of the results. Where the mathematical framework is provided, more detailed scrutiny could yield better recommendation tools. For example, a framework is proposed in [3] aimed at assessing the potential of soil by means of equations and clear criteria.

We highlight that no article deals with all, or even most, of the crop lifecycle, and applications are restricted to a specific aspect of the agricultural process. Research on the connection between the crop lifecycle is required. For example, in [10] the authors dealt with fertilization, pest control, and watering stages of the plant lifecycle, and the proposed approach can be expanded to include other stages.

The interfaces of GIS-based RSs in agriculture and marketing or e-commerce do not seem to have been explored academically, but they show promise. For example, in [22], advertisements of optimal pesticides to the user could be shown.

The social use of the RSs is evidenced as half of the applications deal with modernization and come from developing countries [1, 5, 8, 28, 4, 9, 17, 20, 21, 30, 6, 27, 23].

Although no application domain showed a high number of publications, watering and pest control seem to be even more neglected, as only three research works [10, 4, 22] addressed these important stages of agricultural production.

The automatic analysis by the Python routine yielded several meaningful insights. One of the strongest positive correlations was found between the use of pest control and watering (0.46), followed closely by the correlation between fertilization and watering (0.43). These values suggest that certain aspects of the crop lifecycle tend to be addressed in tandem, particularly those associated with on-the-ground agricultural maintenance. The co-occurrence of these features may reflect integrated approaches to optimizing crop health, especially in systems where environmental monitoring and responsive input application are more advanced.

Another notable correlation is between crop recommendation and the modernization goal (0.39). This aligns with our earlier qualitative analysis, which showed that many papers aiming to modernize agricultural practices also focused on suggesting suitable crops for specific conditions. This relationship highlights how technology-driven recommendations are being used as entry points to promote innovation, particularly in regions where agriculture is not yet fully mechanized or digitized.

In contrast, management-oriented studies tend to correlate more with soil selection (0.35), reinforcing the idea that such works aim to refine already existing, mature systems through better resource assessment and optimization.

Interestingly, the strongest negative correlations also provide valuable insight. For instance, modernization is negatively correlated with soil selection (-0.35), suggesting that when papers aim to modernize agricultural practices, they may be overlooking the foundational role of soil assessment. Similarly, management goals are negatively associated with watering (-0.31) and crop recommendation (-0.39), perhaps indicating a missed opportunity to integrate newer lifecycle stages into already advanced agricultural systems.

These inverse relationships may reflect a gap in current research: namely, the need for approaches that bridge foundational inputs (like soil and water) with both modernization and refinement goals. Bridging these gaps could be key to developing more comprehensive and resilient GIS-based recommender systems in agriculture.

Table 1: Classification Table of GIS-based RS Papers

Ref.	THE	APP	MOD	MNG	SSL	CRE	FER	PCT	WAT	YPD	CLI	SOH	COM	DES	MAT
ANLEY & TESEMA, 2019	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
CHEBOTAREV et al., 2020	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
DOSHI et al., 2018	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
FARHEEN, 2021	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
GAO et al., 2018	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
IYER et al., 2019	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
MUPANGWA et al., 2020	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
SUCHITHRA & PAI, 2020	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
TINOCO et al., 2019	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
YUSIANTO & HARDJOMIDJOJO, 2020	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
ZERMAS et al., 2020	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
DABRE et al., 2018	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
FEGADE & PAWAR, 2019	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
PRIYADHARSHINI et al., 2021	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
RAMCHANDANI et al., 2020	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
RIZALDI et al., 2019	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
RAHMAN & MITRA, 2018	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
OSMAN et al., 2020	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
PETERS et al., 2020	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
RODRÍGUEZ-GARCÍA et al., 2020	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
PRASAD et al., 2021	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
ED-DAOUDI et al., 2023	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
AVEZBOYEV et al., 2023	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
EZRA et al., 2023	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
YUDHANA et al., 2023	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
NUNGULA et al., 2023	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0

5 Related Work

We found two works in the peer-reviewed literature that we consider related to our review, i.e., literature review papers with similar objectives.

[24] present a literature review on disruptive technologies, focusing on Artificial Intelligence (AI) in agriculture. Although the authors mention GIS and RS in passing, these technologies are not the core focus of their analysis. Their study examines the transformative impact of AI-driven AgriTech on agriculture, emphasizing the shift from traditional farming to smart, data-driven, and sustainable practices aligned with the Fourth Industrial Revolution. AgriTech is categorized into three main types: (i) **Physical**, including robotics and machinery; (ii) **Cyber**, involving software solutions such as data analytics; and (iii) **Cyber-physical**, which merges the two to enhance decision-making through predictive analytics. According to the authors, technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, drones, and Machine Learning (ML) enable precision agriculture by optimizing processes, increasing yield, and improving sustainability.

[6] present a literature review on Machine Learning algorithms used in agriculture. The study compares five models: Decision Tree, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine. Evaluation metrics include precision, recall, F1-score, and accuracy, offering a comprehensive assessment of each model’s performance in predicting the most suitable crop based on environmental data such as soil nutrients, temperature, and precipitation. These objectives align with the goals of our review, albeit from a machine learning perspective. Among the tested algorithms, Random Forest yielded the best results.

6 Conclusion

This paper presented a systematic literature review focusing on the intersection of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Recommender Systems (RS) within the context of agriculture. By adopting the methodology proposed by [12], we conducted a structured and replicable process for the selection, evaluation, and classification of studies. From an initial pool of 233 works retrieved from IEEE Xplore and Springer Link, a final corpus of 26 studies was selected based on explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria. These works were analyzed through a multi-dimensional framework considering factors such as methodological approach, intended goal (modernization vs. management), crop lifecycle stage, GIS utilization, and presentation style.

The review reveals that GIS-based RSs in agriculture remain an emerging and under-explored research area, particularly when compared with their applications in domains like e-commerce or entertainment. Most reviewed studies address isolated aspects of the agricultural process—mainly crop recommendation and fertilization—indicating a lack of

integrated approaches spanning the full crop lifecycle. Additionally, although climate-related GIS data is widely used due to its accessibility, the cost and complexity of soil data acquisition hinder its broader adoption, despite its critical importance for accurate recommendations.

A significant number of studies originate from developing countries and target the modernization of non-optimized agricultural practices. This underscores the social relevance of RSs in agriculture, especially in contexts where mechanization and informatization are still evolving. However, the predominance of descriptive over mathematical presentations and the limited reproducibility of experimental frameworks restrict broader adoption and scaling. Notably, the few studies that do incorporate mathematical modeling (e.g., [3]) stand out as valuable contributions to replicable and scalable system design.

Correlation analysis performed using a Python-based prototype revealed patterns and associations between categorical features across studies, complementing our qualitative review. Positive correlations were observed between modernization goals and crop recommendation, as well as between watering and pest control—suggesting recurring functional pairings in RS design. Conversely, negative correlations such as between modernization and soil selection point to overlooked areas in current research. These findings highlight the need for holistic models that connect foundational agricultural elements (e.g., soil, water) with advanced intelligent recommendation strategies.

Additionally, we identify several research gaps:

1. The absence of RSs addressing the entire agricultural lifecycle.
2. Limited integration of GIS-based RSs with e-commerce or marketing platforms, which could significantly enhance usability and impact.
3. Underrepresentation of certain lifecycle stages such as watering and pest control.

These gaps present fertile ground for future research, particularly for interdisciplinary teams integrating expertise from agronomy, geographic systems, and AI-driven decision support.

As a future direction, we propose the development of a GIS-based RS for agricultural supply recommendation, addressing critical inputs such as fertilizers, tools, and machinery. This tool would deliver context-specific recommendations tailored to local soil and climate conditions, grounded in a robust system architecture and the insights from this literature review.

We hope that this study will serve as a foundational reference for researchers and practitioners working to advance intelligent, GIS-aware decision support systems in agriculture—ultimately promoting sustainability, productivity, and socio-economic development.

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